

CURRENT STATE OF THE BULGARIAN OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS

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Abstract

Introduction: Open access to knowledge is becoming a priority area of development and a logical choice for access to reliable information. It contributes to the development of a new way of communication through the free sharing of scientific publications to any interested reader. The idea of the possibility of e-publications being available on the Internet for free to the end user dates to the 1990s, when William Gardner proposed that psychology journals to be published online using the term “electronic archive”, hence the need for quality information is something long needed. Open access is an initiative for the immediate and free online access to scientific results, without the limitations imposed by the copyright and agreements with publishers.

Goal: The paper is divided into two parts: theoretical and practicably analytical. The theoretical part presents the three key initiatives for the future of open access carried out during the meetings held in Budapest (2001), Bedesta (2003) and Berlin (2003). The practicably analytical part includes the current development of the open access initiatives in Bulgaria, such as the project “Education for Tomorrow” by the Ministry of Education and Science, also the Bulgarian Portal for Open Science, which is in line of the Bulgarian engagement to contribute in EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) and in the frame of realization of two national strategies – “Bulgaria National Roadmap for Research Infrastructure, 2017-2023” and NSDSR (“National Strategy for Development of Scientific Research in the Republic of Bulgaria 2017 – 2030: Better Science for Better Bulgaria”), etc. A comparative analysis of the Bulgarian journals in the period 2003 – 2021, the quantity and quality data were collected from the site of the DOAJ and are presented in tables and graphics, based on different criteria – used license (form of Creative Commons), language, etc.

The methodology for achieving the main objective of the study and solving the set research tasks include the following specific methods: content analysis, comparative analysis; synthesis of the obtained information.

Conclusion: Open access returns us to the values of science: to help advance and improve society. The benefits of open access, open source, and open standards are numerous. Hence, the need for and implementation of institutional open access policies as well as suggestions for the future development of open access in Bulgaria are discussed.

Keywords: open access, open science, DOAJ, Bulgaria, Bulgarian Portal for Open Science, open access journals